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TITLE OF THE REPORT:
ADVENTURE TOURISM IN
HIMACHAL PRADESH AND ITS
CHALLENGES FACED BY
TOURISTS

BROADER AREA: ADVENTURE
TOURISM

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OBJECTIVES OF THE REPORT:

- To highlight the concept of adventure tourism.
- To study and examine adventure tourism in Himachal Pradesh.
- To trace out some challenges of adventure tourism in the Himachal Pradesh and to point out some suggestions

INTRODUCTION

Adventure tourism in Himachal Pradesh has emerged out as one of the most important industries of India. Recently it has been observed that there is a lot of potential for the development of the adventure activities. Himachal Pradesh has the natural beauty, peaceful natural environment, thick forests and wildlife, sacred shrines and historical monuments which is a boon for adventurous activities. It is also a land of mysticism in Himalayan region, which is unique and peculiar in the perspective of promotion of adventure tourism in many ways as it attracts a large number of tourists throughout the world. If adventure tourism industry also benefits the economical growth of the state. Himachal Pradesh is the land of the high hills and deep gorges, every nook and corner of the state is a playing field for adventure lovers. Whether a person wants to jump off cliffs or fly above the clouds, or you want to play with stirring waters, you can come here anytime and thrill the senses. Bir Billing, Manali, Spiti Valley, Dalhousie, Shimla are the destination where a person can opt for adventure activities. The major challenges faced by the tourists or adventure enthusiasts are inadequacy of transport facilities, lack of good infrastructure facilities, risk factors and lack of safety measures. These challenges identified should be not only traced but also must be eliminated by taking the necessary measures like to facilitate some protection quality, to frame out strict rules to make the adventure tourism eco-friendly, to improve infrastructure facilities like washrooms, roads, hotels, taxis, parking, etc for the tourists. This research paper gives a glance of the adventure tourism and its challenges faced in Himachal Pradesh. Adventure tourism is branch of ecotourism and is based on nature and natural environment and wilderness of the destination, involving exploration or travel to remote areas, where the traveller expects the unexpected. Adventure tourism is rapidly gaining popularity as tourists seek unusual holidays, different from the typical sightseeing or just visiting any destination for a change. Adventure means different things to different people but for the people who have the nature of exploring new things and new areas, tourism word finds its place beside the adventure and the meaning of this combo gets changed, and the fore vision of exploring new destinations and the adventurous activities come in the mind automatically. Mountaineering expeditions, trekking, bungee jumping, sky diving, parasailing, ballooning, rafting and rock climbing are the activities can be done under adventure tourism.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The state of Himachal Pradesh is blessed with immense beauty. The state has been a popular tourist destination for years now due to its flawless beauty and scenic splendour. However, it is gradually emerging as a popular trekking destination among adventure enthusiasts. The diverse terrain of the state allows for a number of adventure activities, of which trekking is the most popular. Irrespective of experience at trekking, Himachal trekking trails tests capability and limits while offering some of the best panoramic views of the Himalayan mountain range. Adventure tours in Himachal Pradesh are for people of all ages and of varied tastes in terms of activities. Most of such activities make use of hills in some or the other way, as much of the state is mountainous. The altitude in the state ranges from roughly 450 meters to 6500 meters, accounting for a substantial variation in climate. Whenever a traveller comes to any of the places in the state, he will find some or the other activity being organized. With so much to explore and the beautiful landscape to encourage, the sense of adventure inadvertently boosts the travellers. There are so many adventure sports to choose from that keep one on his toes and leave feeling thrilled and filled with elation. So, given he

re are some of the adventure activities offered as the adventure tourism products by the industry in Himachal Pradesh.

SOFT ADVENTURE - Camping:Some, of the best camping sites in Himachal Pradesh are Chail in Shimla, Tabo in Spiti and Sangla valley. There are many camping projects organized by the Himachal government and private sector. Himachal Tourism camps are Sangla in Kinnaur, Kalpa in Kinnaur, Kazza in Spiti, Camps run by Youth Association of India are Dalhousie, Kullu, Manali, and Camps run by private sector are Baspa in Sangla valley, Kalpa in Kinnaur, Taragarh in Kagra, Baldian near Shimla etc.

Zorbing: Zorbing is one of the newer adventure sports of India but quite fun and exciting. Zorbing is typically rolling down a hill slope in a fairly large and light ball called a zorb. It can be enjoyed at Solang valley in Manali.

HARD ADVENTURE - Trekking: The numerous paths thick forests, with rivulets and snow clad mountains, make the trekking worth it. There are about 270 trekking trails in Himachal of which following are the most popular: In district Chamba, near Dalhousie, Dainkund Peak, (2755 m), is the highest mountain peak in Dalhousie, Khajjiar often known as the Switzerland of India, it is situated at an altitude of 1951 meters in the foothills, Kalatop Khajjiar, Manimahesh are most visited and famous trakes. In district Kangra, Triyund Hill Trek, Bhagsunaag lake trek. In district Kullu Bijli Mahadev Temple at the hill top just above the kullu town at an altitude of 2460 meters, Kasol in Manikaran Valley at an altitude of 1640 meters, Beas Kund trek 4000meters. Brigu lake 4500 meters, Rohtang Pass 3978

meters, Solang valley trek, Malana Trek are most visited treks and easy to moderate in nature and the part soft adventures in Himachal Pradesh.

Mountain Biking: Mountain biking is relatively new to our country. It comprises of cycling on un-metalled tracks of the state or even cross country. Some of the best trails for cycling in the mountains are Leh-Manali highway, Manali-Dimphug, Tabo-Kaza, Kaza-Losar, Shimla-Rampur and Rampur-Sangla are offered for mountain biking.

River Rafting & other water sports: The presence of several glacial rivers in Himachal makes it ideal for multitude water sports like river rafting, rowing etc. The thrill of indulging in these fast paced adventure sports in the white water is beyond what words can explain. Satluj River in Shimla, Chenab in Lahaul valley, River Beas near Kullu valley, Ravi near Chamba, are some famous destinations for river rafting.

Skiing: This is one sport that draws tourists and adventure seekers to Himachal Pradesh. The snow draped slopes of Himalayas like Shivalik, Pir Panjal and Dhauladhar are ideal for the sport. Best time for skiing is winters, especially the months of mid December to February. Skiing enthusiast can satiate himself at Kufri in Shimla (**Annual Winter Sports festival held here in February**), Solang valley in Manali. Lahaul and Spiti district, as called as cold desert, is having nice and longer slopes but the accessibility and the road connectivity is hampering its skiing potential.

Heli Skiing: A more exigent form of skiing, heli skiing is done at much higher altitudes on the mountain slopes that are far less explored and on soft snow as compared to the harder one as seen in case of normal skiing. If an enthusiast wants to take skiing to a higher level and test his skills even more he can explore the places like Deo Tibba, Rohtang pass, Chanderkhani pass, Hanuman Tibba and Chandrakhani pass.

Para Gliding & Hang Gliding: Para gliding and hang gliding are two sports that give thrill and a feeling like a carefree wandering bird, soaking in the fresh and mystical air of the mountains. If travellers are interested, Himachal Aero Institute in Bilaspur would prove great to give a head start. Here are some places where visitors can engage in these sports Bir in Kangra valley, Bundla dhar in Bilaspur, Bijli Mahadeo in Bhunter, Manali, Arhaul Solang valley in Kullu.

Mountaineering and Rock Climbing: The mountainous topography of Himachal Pradesh has blessed the state with ample cliffs, hills and rocks that are ideal for rock climbing and mountaineering, most of which is done in Manali itself. Manali also has an institute named Atal Bihari Vajpayee Institute for Mountaineering and Allied Sports where one can get training for the same. It also carries out many mountaineering expeditions from time to time, viz. Shitidhar Expedition, Deo Tibba Expedition and Hanuman Tibba Expedition, Friendship peak expedition etc.

Rappelling: It can be seen as the opposite of rock climbing. This is an adventure sport where one has to descend a steep incline or cliff in a controlled manner utilizing the help of a rope. Mostly the places where rock climbing is done also made for rappelling. Some of the places where these two sports are carried out are Manali, Beas Kund region, Chandrabhaga range, Pir panjal, Dhauladhar range etc.

RESEARCH QUESTION

Q. The service supply in himachal for adventure tourism activities is less than that of tourist demand?

CAUSES

- Inadequate infrastructure
- Improper training of adventure trainers
- Improper facilities for tourists
- Lack of Destination management
- Improper Disaster management

SOLUTIONS

- Improvement of air, road and rail connectivity.
- Proper education training to adventure trainees.
- Restrictions of inflow of the tourists.
- Development of hotels (luxury).
- Proper training and awareness for disaster management.

CONCLUSION

The adventure component of such tour products is recognizable by the activity and sometimes also by the location. White water rafting and kayaking, skiing and snowboarding, hiking and biking, climbing and mountaineering, sailing and paragliding all of these form the basis for adventure tours. Here, the term adventure tourism means a guided commercial tour, where the principal attraction is an outdoor activity that relies on features of the natural terrain, generally requires specialized sporting or similar equipment, and is exciting for the tour clients. There are tens or hundreds of thousands of individual adventure tourism products worldwide, and many millions of tourists buying them each year. And adventure tours are rarely cheap, not least because they commonly require expensive specialist equipment like hiking boots, backpacks, tents etc. It can't be affordable to an average tourist that's why it is important to know how adventure tourists are different from tourists in general. For tourism to be adventure tourism tourists has to take part in

activities where risk is involved and a challenge is perceived, in a natural environment. To operate the activities in successful manner customer has to be satisfied and it depends on guides and service, so people are also critical to the commercial success of adventure tourism. In my research I have found that the development of adventure tourism in India is comparatively new phenomenon as comparing to the neighboring nation Nepal. In spite of starting and adopting the adventure tourism so late, India has emerged as one of the best adventure destinations in the world. Maximum of the activities are carried out in the Himalayan region because the natural set up for the adventure activities is best in this region. Ministry of Tourism is also greatly concerned to develop adventure tourism in the country. For that the authority issues guidelines and establishes norms time to time. Long stretch of the Himalayan range makes the nation a most favorite destination for the adventure activities and attracts millions of foreign as well as domestic tourists. But here I found problem which is hampering the growth of this form of tourism in the nation. The problem is gap between the demand and service. Demand is higher but the accommodation and the capacity still has to be developed.

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